

COMPARATIVE SEASONAL ANALYSIS OF PHYSIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS AND PHYTOPLANKTON SPECIES COMPOSITION IN BATTICALOA LAGOON AND KANDY LAKE

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ABSTRACT

Batticaloa Lagoon is a very large estuarine lagoon with brackish water in Batticaloa District, Sri Lanka. It is a long and narrow lagoon situated in the East coast of Sri Lanka with the total area is 11,500 ha of water. The Surface area is 141.18 sq.kilometers and the highest depth is 4 meters. The lagoon is 56 km long and opens into the sea at two points. One in the southern end of the lagoon at Periyakallar and the other is midway of the lagoon at Palameenmadu which is close to the Batticaloa town.

Water samples were collected in two seasons i.e., in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) at two sampling locations, which are A (Eravur) and B (Koddamunai bridge area). When compare to previous year (2020 / The Government imposed lockdown and curfew for a long period) the pollution level was increased in the year 2021. Higher numbers of phytoplankton members were recorded in dry season than rainy season.

Kandy Lake is a freshwater ornamental artificial Lake in the heart of the hill city of Kandy, Sri Lanka. The total surface area is 19ha. The surface area is 0.006544 sq. kilometers. The circumference is 3.21 km. The highest depth is 18.5 meters. Kandy Lake is artificial and was created in 1807 by Sri Wickrama Rajasinha, the last ruler of the kingdom of Kandy.

Water samples were collected in two seasons i.e., in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) at two sampling locations which are A (Kandy City Center area) and B (Department of Immigration & Emigration area). In both seasons same number (08) of phytoplankton members were recorded in both sampling locations A (Kandy City Center area) and B (Department of Immigration & Emigration area). The density of phytoplankton members was reduced in rainy season in both sampling locations.

During the study period in the year 2021, no algal bloom was recorded at both sampling stations of Batticaloa Lagoon and Kandy Lake.

Keyword: Phytoplankton, Zooplankton, Larvae, Algal bloom, Physio-chemical, Genus, Species diversity, Species density, Species composition, Estuary, Sand bar, Streams, Taxa, Euphotic zone, Epipelagic zone, Protista, Cyanobacteria, Photosynthetic bacteria, Oligotrophic, Mesotrophic, Eutrophic, Hypereutrophic.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Phytoplankton

Phytoplankton obtain their energy through photosynthesis, as do trees and other plants on land. This means phytoplankton must have light from the sun, so they live in the well-lit surface layers (euphotic zone) of oceans and lakes. In comparison with terrestrial plants, phytoplankton are distributed over a larger surface area, are exposed to less seasonal variation and have markedly faster turnover rates than trees (days versus decades). As a result, phytoplankton respond rapidly on a global scale to climate variations.

Phytoplankton is a plant plankton which cannot move actively and changes location depending on the movement of water. Phytoplankton communities are widely spreaded from aquatic to terresial lands. Plankton form the first ring of food chain in aquatic environment effecting the efficiency of this environment. Daily, seasonally and yearly changes are important for calculating efficiency in aquatic fields. Phytoplankton composition is a trophic indication of the water mass. In addition, phytoplankton species are used as an indicator for determining the nutrient level which is the basis for preparing and monitoring the strategies of the lake management in the lakes. Using phytoplankton communities or other aquatic organisms for evaluating water quality is based on very ancient times. Saprobic (feeds on dead or decaying organic matter) and trophic indicator types are used in many researches (Thunmark.S.1945 and Lepistö.L.Rosenström.U.1998). In addition, various numerical indices have been developed (Thunmark.S.1945 and Nygaard.G.1949). However, none of them have been accepted extensively. This is caused by several reasons.

Phytoplankton communities are influenced by significant changes every year. The competitive environment known as seasonal succession has been changing (Sommer.U.1986). If the conditions don't change, this process results in the choice of communities dominated by one or more species. Phytoplankton responds rapidly to the condition changes. Conditional changes will result the formation of high compositional diversity (Scheffer. M. Reinaldi S.Huisman. J. Weissing.F.J.2003).

The first approaches to classify algal communities don't have wide range of application in determining water quality. Pankin's approaches to classify algal communities in 1941 and 1945 weren't generally accepted (Padisak.J.Grigorszky.I.Borics.G.Soroczki-pinter.E.2006). (Reynolds.C. S. 1980 and 1997) applied a classic phytosociological approach to phytoplankton data obtained from the lakes in northeast England and classified them into various communities. (Sommer.U.1986) found high similarities among the compositions of species and seasonal succession of Alpine lakes. (Mason.C. F.1991) reported that oligotrophic and eutrophic lakes have the communities of characteristic phytoplankton. There are qualitative differences among phytoplankton communities in oligotrophic and eutrophic lakes. The composition and the phytoplankton communities are affected by environmental conditions.

For example, a numerical decrease is observed in *Anabaena* and *Aphanizomenon* species from heterocyst blue-green algae found in mesotrophic lake layers with a decrease of nitrogen saturation in the lakes. In addition, there are differences among the environmental conditions preferred by *Diatoms*, *Dinoflagellate* or *Cosmarium*, *Pandorina* and *Gemmellicystis* species, even though they can be found in the lakes with same level of nutrients (Reynolds.C.Dokulil.M.Padisak.J.2000).

Anabaena *Aphanizomenon*

Diatoms *Dinoflagellates* *Cosmarium* *Pandorina* *Gemmellicystis*

1.2. Importance of Phytoplankton

Phytoplankton are tiny photosynthetic organisms that are the major producers of marine and fresh water life. They form the foundation of the food web for most marine and fresh water life. They are responsible for half of the photosynthetic activity on earth, making them important to both their local and the global ecosystems. Their importance in carbon-dioxide sequestration has made them a target for controlling carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. (<https://sciencing.com/importance-phytoplankton-5414740.html>)

Phytoplankton are important to the global ecosystem as well as oceanic and freshwater ecosystems. They are responsible for half of the photosynthetic activity on the planet. This means that of the carbon dioxide in the atmosphere that gets fixed into sugars, phytoplankton are doing half of the work. This makes them important to global carbon-dioxide levels. Without phytoplankton to pull carbon dioxide out of the atmosphere, carbon-dioxide levels would rise, because carbon dioxide would continue to be produced in both biological and industrial sources.

Phytoplankton are the photosynthetic portion of plankton life. Plankton are the tiny, drifting organisms that live in the top layers of ocean and lakes. Because phytoplankton rely on sunlight to produce their own food. This layer, the epipelagic layer, goes down 200 meters. It is defined by the fact that enough light gets through the water to allow for photosynthesis. (<https://sciencing.com/importance-phytoplankton-5414740.html>)

Phytoplankton's role in the global ecosystem has made them a target for controlling carbon-dioxide levels in the earth's atmosphere. Companies such as Climos and Planktos have invested in phytoplankton as a means of reducing carbon-dioxide emissions. They are investigating fertilizing phytoplankton communities with iron, a vital nutrient, to promote their growth. As political and economic pressures to provide carbon-dioxide emissions offsets increases, the potential profit of companies like these increases.

(<https://sciencing.com/importance-phytoplankton-5414740.html>)

Phytoplankton are microscopic little ocean and freshwater drifters, plant-like organisms that photosynthesise and can be found in both marine and freshwater and are present in all of the world's oceans. They live in the euphotic zone (the topmost layer of the ocean) where sunlight is plentiful. There are so many that, if we scooped up of seawater or freshwater probably have as many as 75–100 million individual phytoplankton.

Lake (Freshwater) Ocean (Marine)

Ecosystem

Accompanying the phytoplankton in this mix of ocean and freshwater are the zooplankton, which are tiny animals – some are the larval stages of much bigger creatures, others will remain as just tiny animals. All plankton are unable to swim against the water currents and so they float with the help of the water waves. However, there are areas where more phytoplankton occur, usually where upwelling (deep, cold water rises up to the surface) brings essential nutrient-rich water to the surface. (<https://www.howitworksdaily.com/the-importance-of-phytoplankton/>)

Zooplankton Larvae Tiny Animals Upwelling Nutrients

Phytoplankton are crucial for life on Earth —it's almost unimaginable to think of a world without them. The tiny organisms form the basis of the entire oceanic and freshwater food web, photosynthesizing to turn sunlight into energy and providing food for small filter-feeders and grazers, which in turn are food for larger animals, including the fish.

The phytoplankton also have a huge impact on our atmosphere as they are responsible for producing at least 50 per cent of Earth's oxygen. They are also an important carbon sink, taking in carbon dioxide from the atmosphere that is then pulled to the bottom of the ocean when the phytoplankton dies. Over millions of years these plankton (along with other marine and freshwater creatures and organic matter) build up in layers on the seabed, which, under intense pressure and heat, can form oil or natural gas. (<https://www.howitworksdaily.com/the-importance-of-phytoplankton/>).

1.3. Phytoplankton as Bio-indicator

Phytoplankton are the first bio- indicators of pollution in aquatic ecosystems. Phytoplankton assemblage and aquatic ecosystems are always influenced by environmental factors therefore these environmental changes and threats must be understood in any ecosystem. Phytoplankton are inexpensive and readily available bio- indicators. (Pourafrasyabi, M. and Ramezanzpour, Z. 2014)

Anthropogenic activities have affected the water quality in many natural and artificial water bodies, including lakes and reservoirs during recent decades. This has had both a quantitative and qualitative effect on the water needed for social and economic purposes. Proper water management strongly depends on the long term monitoring of the hydrology and water quality freshwaters (Kennedy 1999).

The phytoplankton community plays a key role in aquatic ecosystems and provides basic requirements such as carbon fixation, oxygen production as well as food generation (Fathi et al. 2001; Khan 2003). Phytoplankton are important primary producers in aquatic systems that could be assigned as efficient bio-indicators of water quality (Peerapornpisal et al. 2004). Phytoplankton species are able to survive and adapt to different habitat conditions, although each specific species has a defined niche according to its physiological requirements and the limits imposed by environmental conditions. In temperate waters, phytoplankton succession is strongly linked to meteorological phenomena, water stratification, seasonal cycling, and patterns of population distribution (Wetzel. 2001). For instance, some species are highly dominant in eutrophic waters, whereas others are very sensitive to environmental changes. Thus, the diatoms *Melosira* and *Cyclotella* usually exist in clean freshwaters, while *Nitzschia*, *Microcystis* and *Aphanizomenon* are commonly found in polluted waters (Rice et al. 2012).

Melosira

Cyclotella

Nitzschia *Microcystis* *Aphanizomenon*

The species of *Chlamydomonas*, *Euglena* and *Scenedesmus* (Prescott 1973), and *Microcystis* (Prescott 1973; Peerapornpisal et al. 2004) are indicators of eutrophic waters. Reynolds and Lund 2006 reported that *Aphanizomenon*, *Microcystis* and *Ceratium* can inhabit waters high in phosphate and *Anabaena* is found in waters with a slight nitrogen content. Some blue-green algae such as *Microcystis*, *Anabaena*, *Anabaenopsis*, *Aphanizomenon* and *Cylindrospermopsis* produce toxic components and algal bloom that may affect water quality and ecosystem health (Hitzfeld et al. 2000; Cook et al. 2004). Furthermore, they may cause a problem with taste, unfavorable odors and high water turbidity (Borgh 2004).

Chlamydomonas *Euglena* *Scenedesmus* *Microcystis*

Aphanizomenon *Microcystis* *Ceratium*

Microcystis *Anabaena* *Anabaenopsis* *Aphanizomenon* *Cylindrospermopsis*

1.4. Batticaloa Lagoon

Batticaloa Lagoon is a very large estuarine lagoon in Batticaloa District, Eastern Sri Lanka. The city of Batticaloa is located on land between the lagoon and the Indian Ocean. Batticaloa District is flourished with three lagoons, such Batticaloa lagoon, Valaichchenai Lagoon and Vakari Lagoon. Among them, Batticaloa lagoon is the largest lagoon in Batticaloa District. Batticaloa lagoon is a long and narrow lagoon situated in the East coast of Sri Lanka with the total area of approximately 11,500 ha of water. The lagoon is 56 km long. This lagoon extends from Eravur (Batticaloa District) in the north to Kalmunai (Ampara District) in the south. This lagoon opens into the sea at two points. One in the southern end of the lagoon at Kallar and the other is midway of the lagoon at Palameenmadu, which is close to the Batticaloa town. (Shanmugaratnam, N. 1995) Both are narrow and approximately 200 m wide.

The width of the water flow at their openings varies with the seasons. During the dry season the width of the bar mouth of the lagoon decreases and gradually it get closed with the onset of the north east monsoon which piles up the sand bar by the end of dry season. Later with the rains and with the lagoon mouth closed. The lagoon is fed by a number of small Rivers. It is linked to the sea by a two narrow Channels, one at Batticaloa and the other at Periyakallar. During the dry season these channels are blocked by Sand bars.

At Palameenmadu Bar mouth opened and closed At Pariyakallar causeway

The lagoon is surrounded by a densely populated region used for cultivating rice, coconut and other crops. The surrounding land is used for shrimp farming and rice cultivation. The lagoon has extensive mangrove swamps and some sea grass beds. The lagoon attracts a wide variety of water birds. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Batticaloa_Lagoon)

Mangrove vegetation, Water birds, Fishing and Shrimp farming at Batticaloa Lagoon

1.5. Kandy Lake

Kandy Lake also known as Kiri Muhuda or the Sea of Milk, is an artificial Lake in the heart of the hill city of Kandy, Sri Lanka built in 1807 by the King Sri Wickrama Rajasinghe next to the Temple of the Tooth. Over the years, it was reduced in size. It is a protected lake, with fishing banned.

The lake in front of the Temple of the Tooth was formerly a stretch of paddy fields known as Tigolwela. It was converted to a Lake by King Sri Wickrama Rajasingha in 1807. As there had been a pond named *Kiri-muhuda* (a "sea of milk") in the middle of the Tigolwela, the lake

constructed subsequently too was named *Kiri-muhuda*. Deveda Moolacharya is considered the architect of the Kandy Lake. The king first built a dam across the paddy fields, starting from the Paththirippuwa (octagon) side, where the steps leading into the lake by the Mahamaluwa (Esplanade) are still visible, stretching across to the Poya-maluwa. The dam, upon which a roadway was constructed, allowed the king to go across to the Malwatte Vihare. According to D'Oyley, the dam was constructed between 1810 - 1812.

Kiri-muhuda Mahamaluwa

There are numerous local legends and folklore regarding the lake. One such is that the small island at its center was used by the king's harem for bathing and was connected to the palace by a secret tunnel.

The extent of Kandy Lake is 6,544 sq. meters. The circumference is 3.21 km. The highest depth is 18.5 meters. The parapet wall giving the appearance of a cloud, is popularly called *Walakulu Bamma* and measures 633.82 meters. The building located at the center of the lake, together with some ancient ruins, was known as *Diyatilaka Mandapaya* in the past. It is believed that the Kings used this pavilion for relaxation.

Walakulu Bamma past and present view

The Kandy Lake offers a place for a stroll or a jog. The shady path surrounding the lake provides a view of the hills and the town. The Malwatte temple, one of the two head temples of the Siyam Nikaya sect of Theravada Buddhism, is also located overlooking the lake. Pollution of the lake is a serious problem. The government and the surrounding schools are trying to decrease the problem by putting signs and operating environmental societies. Until 1960 the Kandy water board used the lake to distribute water to the surrounding areas. They stopped pumping water from the lake because of the increase in pollution. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kandy_Lake).

Malwatte temple

Siyam

Nikaya

2. OBJECTIVE

In a balanced ecosystem, phytoplanktons provide food for a wide range of sea and freshwater creatures including shrimp, snails, and jellyfish. When too many nutrients are available,

phytoplankton may grow out of control and form harmful algal blooms (HABs). These blooms can produce extremely toxic compounds that have harmful effects on fish, shellfish, mammals, birds, and even people.

Phytoplankton are excellent indicators of ecological change. They are relatively easy to detect, identify, and quantify; they conduct a large share of primary production; and they are sensitive to diverse environmental stressors. (Hans W. Paerl et al. 2007).

Phytoplankton communities are sensitive to alterations in their habitats, and thereby, phyto-plankton total biomass and many phytoplankton species are utilized as indicators of aquatic habitat qualifications (Chellappa et al., 2009) Phytoplankton/algal communities give more evidences concerning alterations in water quality than nutrient or chlorophyll-a concentration. Water quality is a whole of physical, chemical, and biological properties of the water (EEA, 1999).

The monitoring of phytoplankton and algae is of great significance because the monitoring based solely on physical and chemical analysis is sometimes insufficient. The phytoplankton composition not only demonstrates the certain situation of the waters but also the previous situations of aquatic ecosystem. Phytoplankton demonstrates water quality through changes in its community composition, and distribution, and proportion of sensitive species (Gharib et al., 2011).

Phytoplankton are largely governed by light, nutrients, temperature, community structure life-cycle history, stratification or vertical mixing and tides (Alvarez-Góngora & Herrera-Silveira, 2005). Palmer (1969) listed ten most tolerant algal species in order of decreasing tolerance as *Euglena viridis*, *Nitzschiapalea*, *Oscillatorialimosa*, *Scenedesmusquadricauda*, *Oscillatoria tenuis*, *Stigeocloniumtenuue*, *Synedra ulna*, *Ankistrodesmusfalcatius*, *Pandorinamorom*, *Oscillatoriachlorinaw* with their tolerance.

Euglena viridis *Nitzschiapalea* *Oscillatorialimosa* *Scenedes musquadricauda*

Oscillatoria tenuis *Stigeoclonium tenue* *Synedra ulna* *Ankistrodesmusfalcatius*

Pandorinamorum Oscillatoriachlorina

The influence of environmental factors on the seasonal abundance and diversity of plankton biotypes varies significantly, with physical factors like temperature and light intensity being the most important and chemical factors like dissolved oxygen, pH, salinity, hardness, electrical conductivity and nutrient level being of lesser importance (Reynolds, 1984).

As algae have a very broad area of distribution in aquatic environments, they can be very important source of oxygen in these environments, and they are providing food for all other organisms ranging from benthic invertebrates to fish (Round, 1984). However, overpopulation of algae would take place due to discharge of nutrients into aquatic ecosystems (Akköz & Güler, 2004).

The objective of the present study was to determine;

1. the phytoplankton composition, species diversity & the density of different phytoplankton species of the lagoon in different seasons.
2. the role of physio – chemical properties on the occurrence of phytoplankton assemblage in the lagoon water.
3. the sequence of changes in their biomass with the nutrient enrichment of the lagoon due to releases from the catchments.
4. the condition of the lagoon water during blooms.
5. the possibility of using species diversity & density of phytoplankton in the lagoon and diversity indices for the prediction of water quality using phytoplankton as environmental indicators.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Study area and sampling locations of Batticaloa lagoon and Kandy Lake

Batticaloa Lagoon is a large estuarine lagoon (Brackish water) in Batticaloa District of the Eastern Province in Sri Lanka. It is the largest out of three lagoons in Batticaloa, stretching up to 56 km in length. It extends all the way from Eravur in the Batticaloa district to Kalmunai in the Ampara district. The Batticaloa Lagoon has highly picturesque landscapes and scenic views of the ocean, with many diverse species of exotic flora and fauna, especially a wide variety of migratory, resident, and endemic bird. Also home to Bone Island, Puliyantheevu Island and Buffalo Island, the scenic bridges that allow visitors to cross the lagoon and the Lady Manning Bridge are equally intriguing attractions. Head to the nearby Kallady Bridge Area during the months from April to September to hear the famous ‘singing fish’ during your tour of the area.

Batticaloa lagoon receives waters from eight rivers which are Mundani River, Magalavettuvan River, Vett River, Pathathe River, Mandipattu River, Namakada River, Thumpankeni River, and Andella River. The water quality of the lagoon gets deteriorated due to the activities of the catchments. The Physical, chemical and biological properties of the lagoon water during monsoon rains & dry seasons were estimated.

Batticaloa Lagoon

Eravur - sampling location (A) Koddamunai bridge area – sampling location (B)

The study area of Batticaloa lagoon is categorized into three basins, which are Northern basin, Southern basin and Intermediate basin. During 2021 investigation period, in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) water samples were collected. The sampling region Eravur (A) is located in Northern basin and the sampling region Koddamunai bridge area (B) is located at intermediate region and close to Batticaloa Main market which is 13.2 km away from the region Eravur (A). During rainy season sea water intrusion (Estuarine) is possible. The water temperature, salinity, conductivity and pH were measured directly at the sampling locations.

Estuary Sea water Intrusion and sand bar mouth

Kandy Lake is a freshwater ornamental water body located in Kandy. The extent of Kandy Lake is 6,544 sq. meters. The circumference is 3.21 km. The highest depth is 18.5 meters. The parapet wall giving the appearance of a cloud. Anthropogenic activities on surrounding catchments of the lake may result different physicochemical conditions leading to severe environmental issues. Kandy Lake is artificial and was created in 1807 by Sri Wickrama Rajasinha, the last ruler of the kingdom of Kandy. Several minor local chiefs protested because their people objected to labouring on the project. In order to stop the protests, they were put to death on stakes in the lake bed. The central island was used as Sri Wickrama Rajasinha’s personal harem. Later the British used it as an ammunition store and added the fortress-style parapet around the perimeter. On the south shore, in front of the Malwatte MahaVihara, the circular enclosure is the monks’ bathhouse.

The Lake dominates the heavenly location with its cascading beauty. A silent stroll especially during the sunset time, enjoying the sounds of nature is a splendid way of coming close to Mother Earth and devouring the blissfulness. Being based next to Temple of the Tooth this is an artificial lake built in 1807 by the Royal King of Sri Lanka. The whole walk is around 2.1 mile and consists of enchanting scenic splendor covered with several rest zones where one can sit and enjoy the harmony and serene beauty of the Temple and the lake. In the midst of the lake there is a small island with palm trees making the lake look more eye arresting. Dominating the town is Kandy Lake. A leisurely stroll around it, with a few stops on the lakeside seats, is a pleasant way to spend a few hours, although diesel-spurting buses careening around the southern edge of the lake can mar the peace somewhat. The nicest part to walk along is the area around the Temple of the Sacred Tooth Relic. Due to some past cases of harassment, single women should not walk here alone after dark.

The study area of Kandy Lakewas (A) close to Kandy City Centre and (B) close to Department of Immigration and Emigration. During 2021 investigation period, in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) water samples were collected. The sampling region (A) close to Kandy City Centre 4 km away from (B) close to Department of Immigration and Emigration via

RajapihillaMawatha. The water temperature, salinity, conductivity and pH were measured directly at the sampling locations.

Water samples were collected at 10 m distance away from the shore by using a boat at half length of secchi disk level. So in dry season two samples from Batticaloa Lagoon and two samples from Kandy Lake, then in wet season two samples from Batticaloa Lagoon and two samples from Kandy Lake, totally 08 water samples were collected in the year 2021 and analyzed. The phytoplankton members were identified at genus level. Due to COVID-19 crisis I was not able to collect water samples routinely due to lockdown and curfew time to time and Kandy Lake is highly protected area and I got special permission from the authorities to collect water samples. Based on the situation permitted and to maintain the uniformity water samples were collected.

3.2. Collection of water samples, Sampling procedure and Estimation of phytoplankton at genus level

Water sampling was carried out during the period of June (dry season) and November (wet season) of the year 2021 and during the investigation period the following physico-chemical and biological parameters were estimated. Water Temperature, Salinity, Conductivity, pH, Total phosphate, Nitrate, Chloride and Phytoplankton species density and species diversity were enumerated at genus level.

The sampling locations were (A) Eravur and (B) Koddamunaibrigge area in Batticaloa Lagoon and (A) close to Kandy City Centre area and (B) close to Department of Immigration and Emigration area (B) in Kandy Lake. At each sampling location secchi depths were determined using a black & white disc of 0.25 m in diameter, operated from the boat for comparative purposes, and then water samples were collected half-length of secchi depth (euphotic or epipelagic zone). The water samples were collected with the help of Kemmerer water sampler with a volume of 2.5 L operated from the boat.

3.3. Phytoplankton composition and enumeration

For phytoplankton studies 2.5 L with the help of Kemmerer water sampler water sample was collected and transferred to 2.5 L Amber bottles, the bottles, which contain water samples, were covered with thin aluminum foil to protect from sunlight and then immediately transferred to laboratory as quick as possible. The 100 ml of the water sample was taken from the amber bottle and treated with Lugol's solution at the rate of 100:1 in order to fix and preserve the phytoplankton for 24 hours. The Lugol's solution was prepared by dissolving 10 g of pure iodine and 20 g of KI in 200 ml of distilled water to which 20 ml glacial acetic acid was added three days prior to sampling. The solution was kept in amber bottles. Iodine, which is usually prepared as Lugol's solution, offers the double advantage of making cells heavy enough to settle. Therefore, the preservation and counting of many flagellates was made possible. Therefore, the most suitable phytoplankton preservative is Lugol's solution, which can be used for all forms including the naked flagellates. The major preservatives in use today (formalin, Lugol's solution, and glutaraldehyde) are discussed. (Wetzel, R. G., & Likens, G.E. 1991).

3.4. Isolation of phytoplankton

From the preserved water sample 90 ml of supernatant was removed carefully by using a syringe and also it was confirmed that the supernatant did not have any algal cells. The remaining concentrated 10 ml of the sample was centrifuged at 4000 r.p.m. for 15 minutes. After centrifuging 9 ml of supernatant was removed carefully by using a syringe and also it was confirmed that the supernatant does not have any algal cells. The final 1 ml concentrated solution of 100 ml sample, was subjected to species composition and algal counts (Anon, 1992a).

Identification was done at genus level by using a key "Phytoplankton Identification" (<http://oceandatacenter.ucsc.edu/PhytoGallery/phytolist.html>). Identification at Genus level was done by the following method. At the beginning the distinguishing features of each species were carefully recorded. In this regard the following identification parameters were considered, which are presence or absence of plastids (prokaryotes or eukaryotes), unicell (motile or non-motile & shape of the cell), colony (motile or non-motile cells), filamentous (shape of cells, presence or absence of any frustule's projections).

3.5. Counting of phytoplankton

Counting of phytoplankton was done by using a Haemocytometer through compound microscope (Olympus / Tokyo No: 615534). From the concentrated 1 ml sample, sub samples were taken using a pipette and placed on the haemocytometer for identification and counting. Counting was done in triplicates for enumeration of phytoplankton density. Observation made through low power ($4 \times 10 \times = 40 \times$) and medium power ($10 \times 10 \times = 100 \times$). The volume of squares of haemocytometer was pre-calculated as follows.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Physico-chemical parameters of Batticaloa Lagoon

4.1.1. Water Temperature

Eravurtown is a coastal city in Sri Lanka. The water temperature measured in June (dry season) in this location (A) was 34°C. The depth in this location is less than 1.5 m. This sampling location (A) receives drainage from the paddy steamer station at Eravur close to the sampling location (A). This may be the reason for high water temperature. The water temperature measured in November (rainy season) in the sampling location was 30 °C.

Eravur Rice Steamer close to Batticaloa Lagoon

The water temperature measured at the sampling location (B) Koddamunai bridge area in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 32 °C and 29 °C respectively. This sampling location is located close to the Batticaloa main market and surrounded by several shops, restaurants, and Batticaloa main Bus stand.

Batticaloa Market close to Koddamunai bridge Batticaloa Bus stand

Batticaloa Market

Koddamunai bridge

4.1.2. Salinity

The salinity measured at the sampling location A (Eravur) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 3 ppt and 2 ppt respectively, and the salinity measured at the sampling location B (Koddamunai bridge area) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 28.5 ppt and 22.9 ppt respectively. The distance from Palameenmadu (Bar mouth) to A (Eravur) is 12.5 Km and the distance from Palameenmadu (Bar mouth) to B (Koddamunai bridge area) is 5.4 Km. It shows clearly the salinity variation.

Distance between Palameenmadu (Bar mouth) and Koddamunai bridge is 5.4 Km

Mahatma Gandhi Park close to Koddamunai bridge

Distance between Palameenmadu (Bar mouth) and Eravur is 12.5 Km Eravur lagoon park

4.1.3. Conductivity

The conductivity measured at the sampling location A (Eravur) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 30.7 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 33.8 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ respectively, and the conductivity measured at the sampling location B (Koddamunai bridge area) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 29.8 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 22.9 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ respectively.

4.1.4. pH

The pH measured at the sampling location A (Eravur) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 9 and 8 respectively, and the conductivity measured at the sampling location B (Koddamunai bridge area) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 8 in both periods.

4.1.5. Total Phosphate

When compare to previous year (2020) there was an increase in the total phosphate content estimated in the sampling locations. The total phosphate content measured at the sampling location A (Eravur) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 0.08 mg/L and 0.07

mg/L respectively, and the total phosphate content measured at the sampling location B (Koddamunai bridge area) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 0.09 mg/L and 0.08 mg/L respectively. The duration of lockdown and curfew in the year 2020 was longer compare to the year 2021. Almost all the schools, restaurants, theaters, markets, shops, industries were closed for a long period but in the year 2021 it was lifted. This may be the reason for the increase of pollution in the year 2021.

4.1.6. Nitrate

When compare to previous year (2020) there was an increase in the nitrate content estimated in the sampling locations. The nitrate measured at the sampling location A (Eravur) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 4.2 mg/L and 3.9 mg/L respectively, and the nitrate content measured at the sampling location B (Koddamunai bridge area) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 4.7 mg/L and 4.2 mg/L respectively. The duration of lockdown and curfew in the year 2020 was longer compare to the year 2021. Almost all the schools, restaurants, theaters, markets, shops, industries were closed for a long period but in the year 2021 it was lifted. This may be the reason for the increase of pollution in the year 2021.

4.1.7. Chloride

When compare to previous year (2020) there was an increase in the chloride content estimated in the sampling locations. The chloride content measured at the sampling location A (Eravur) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 22.2 mg/L and 20.2 mg/L respectively, and the chloride content measured at the sampling location B (Koddamunai bridge area) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 23.4 mg/L and 21.7 mg/L respectively. The duration of lockdown and curfew in the year 2020 was longer compare to the year 2021. Almost all the schools, restaurants, theaters, markets, shops, industries were closed for a long period but in the year 2021 it was lifted. This may be the reason for the increase in the pollution level in the year 2021 in the Batticaloa Lagoon.

4.2. Physico-chemical parameters of Kandy Lake

Kandy Lake is a source of drinking water for the town, it was observed that a large number of effluent channels drained in to it, carrying a continuous flow of contaminated water. The pH of water remained almost neutral and provided ideal conditions for bacterial growth. field experiments indicated eutrophic conditions in the lake and the unsuitability of water in the unpurified state for drinking purposes. The purified water had a zero coliform count, but the chlorine content added was relatively high and may also prove to be a health hazard. On the whole, the polluted water in Kandy Lake indicated the adversities of human involvements with nature.

(Dissanayake.C.B., Senaratne.A., Weerasooriya.S.V.R., De Silva.S.H.G. 1982).

Kandy Lake is part of the Mahaweli River catchment, which covers 15% of Sri Lanka. The river is the country's longest and a major water source – e.g., for Kandy (Hewavisenthi 1997). The lake drains into the Mid-Canal and then the river. The water supply intake for Katugastota Water Treatment Plant is 4 km downstream of the canal's discharge.

4.2.1. Water Temperature

The water temperature measured at the sampling location A (close to Kandy City Centre) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 25.4°C and 24.3 °C respectively, and the water temperature measured at the sampling location B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigrations) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 25.2 °C and 24.2 °C respectively.

4.2.2. Salinity

The salinity measured at the sampling location A (close to Kandy City Centre) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 1.3 ppt and 1 ppt respectively, and the salinity measured at the sampling location B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigrations) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 1.2 ppt and 1 ppt respectively.

4.2.3. Conductivity

The conductivity measured at the sampling location A (close to Kandy City Centre) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 240 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 238 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ respectively, and the conductivity measured at the sampling location B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigrations) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 260 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 249 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ respectively.

4.2.4. pH

The pH measured at the sampling location A (close to Kandy City Centre) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 7.2 and 7.1 respectively, and the pH measured at the sampling location B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigrations) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 7.1 in both sampling locations.

4.2.5. Total Phosphate

The total phosphate content measured at the sampling location A (close to Kandy City Centre) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 0.35 mg/L and 0.36 mg/L respectively, and the total phosphate content measured at the sampling location B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigrations) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 0.38 mg/L and 0.39 mg/L respectively.

4.2.6. Nitrate

The nitrate content measured at the sampling location A (close to Kandy City Centre) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 1.35 mg/L and 1.45 mg/L respectively, and the nitrate content measured at the sampling location B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigrations) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 1.39 mg/L and 1.48 mg/L respectively.

4.2.7. Chloride

The chloride content measured at the sampling location A (close to Kandy City Centre) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 30.6 mg/L and 34.8 mg/L respectively, and the chloride content measured at the sampling location B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigrations) in June (dry season) and November (rainy season) were 31.8 mg/L and 35.2 mg/L respectively.

Physical parameters in June (dry season) 2021 at the sampling locations Eravur (A) and Koddamunai bridge area (B) in Batticaloa Lagoon				
Sampling locations	Water Temp. °C	Salinity ppt	Conductivity µS/cm	pH
Eravur (A)	34	3	30.7	9
Kodd.Brid.Are (B)	32	28.5	33.8	8
Physical parameters in November (rainy season) 2021 at the sampling locations Eravur (A) and Koddamunai bridge area (B) in Batticaloa Lagoon				
Sampling locations	Water Temp. °C	Salinity ppt	Conductivity µS/cm	pH
Eravur (A)	30	2	29.8	8
Kodd.Brid.Are (B)	29	22.9	22.9	8
Physical parameters in June (dry season) 2021 at the sampling locations A (close to Kandy City Center) and B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigration) in Kandy Lake				
Sampling locations	Water Temp. °C	Salinity ppt	Conductivity µS/cm	pH
A	25.4	1.3	240	7.2
B	25.2	1.2	260	7.1
Physical parameters in November (rainy season) 2021 at the sampling locations A (close to Kandy City Center) and B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigration) in Kandy Lake				
Sampling locations	Water Temp. °C	Salinity ppt	Conductivity µS/cm	pH
A	24.3	1	238	7.1
B	24.2	1	249	7.1

In this study, these graphs show clear physical water quality variations of Batticaloa Lagoon and Kandy Lake and also indicating the Kandy Lake is highly polluted by the human activities and surface runoff from various places into the Kandy Lake than Batticaloa Lagoon. Batticaloa Lagoon is an estuary shows salinity variations in dry and rainy seasons.

Electrical Conductivity (EC) is such a thermophysical property of lake water, which has strong interrelationship with pollution level. Experiments carried out at Subhas Sarovar (lake) and Rabindra Sarovar (lake), Kolkata, indicates that EC has a linear relationship with Total Dissolved Solids (TDS). It is also observed that EC increases with increase in TDS, which in turn indicates increased concentration of sulphates and other ions. Therefore, measured value of EC indirectly indicates the level of pollution in lake waters. (Das, Rajib et al. 2006).

Higher conductivity in the dry season and could be due to higher concentrations of dissolved ions in the water bodies at that period. This could be linked to higher water temperature recorded in the dry season which Dixit and Tawari, (2007)

Chemical parameters in June (dry season) 2021 at the sampling locations Eravur (A) and Koddamunai bridge area (B) in Batticaloa Lagoon			
Sampling locations	Total Phosphate mg/L	Nitrate mg/L	Chloride mg/L
Eravur (A)	0.08	4.2	22.2
Kodd.brid.are (B)	0.09	4.7	23.4
Chemical parameters in November (rainy season) 2021 at the sampling locations Eravur (A) and Koddamunai bridge area (B) in Batticaloa Lagoon			
Sampling locations	Total Phosphate mg/L	Nitrate mg/L	Chloride mg/L
Eravur (A)	0.07	3.9	20.2
Kodd.brid.are (B)	0.08	4.2	21.7
Chemical parameters in June (dry season) 2021 at the sampling locations A (close to Kandy City Center) and B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigration) in Kandy Lake			

Sampling locations	Total Phosphate mg/L	Nitrate mg/L	Chloride mg/L
A	0.35	1.35	30.6
B	0.38	1.39	31.8

Chemical parameters in **November (rainy season) 2021** at the sampling locations **A (close to Kandy City Center)** and **B (close to Department of Immigration and Emigration)** in **Kandy Lake**

Sampling locations	Total Phosphate mg/L	Nitrate mg/L	Chloride mg/L
A	0.36	1.45	34.8
B	0.39	1.48	35.2

These graphs indicate both lagoons are polluted but the source of pollution is different. Batticaloa Lagoon is specifically surrounded by paddy lands, crop cultivated lands rather than others (shops, schools, markets, hotels, catchment areas etc.) and during rainy season due to the surface runoff all kinds of fertilizers and detergents are reaching the lagoon. Kandy Lake is located at the center of the heart of the city and surrounded by highly crowded population and the surface runoff from surrounding areas and catchment areas bringing all kinds of pollutants to the Kandy Lake and fishing also banned here.

The concentration of Nutrient (phosphate) was comparatively higher in the dry season than rainy season. This could be due to the washing off and accumulation of inorganic phosphate from fertilizer and the product of the microbial degradation of glyphosate herbicide used on the riparian farmland into the river bed. Higher level of microbial activities enhanced by higher environmental temperature may lead to the release of phosphate locked up in sediment thereby increasing the concentration in the dry season. Bensalem and Boulahrouf, (2013)

Source of Pollution in Batticaloa Lagoon

1 2 3

4 5 6 7

8 9

10

1. Spiritual activities.
2. Fishing activities from bots.
3. Fishing activities at the shore.
4. Fishing during algal blooming.
5. Fishermen cleaning nets.
6. Tourism.
7. Batticaloa town with schools, hotels, theaters, market.
8. Agricultural activities.
9. Environment degradation.
10. Garbage dump at Thiruperunthurat, close to Lagoon.

Recommendation: Public awareness is very important and rule and regulations should be strongly implemented,

Source of Pollution in Kandy Lake

1

2

3

4

5

6

1. Hotels.
2. Spiritual activities.
3. Kandy city and catchment areas.
4. Algal blooming.
5. Sucker fish population for cleaning process.
6. Tourism.

A high coliform count and a high degree of fecal contamination was observed in all water samples obtained from the Kandy Lake and drains.

(Dissanayake.C.B., A. Senaratne., S.V.R.Weerassoriya, and S.H.G.De Silva, 1982).

Recommendation: Public awareness is very important and rule and regulations should be strongly implemented,

Severe algal blooms have occurred periodically on Kandy Lake (Pu *et al.* 2011). The first major incident occurred during the period of British rule, leading to construction of the Mahamaya Silt Trap in 1873 (Karunaratna. 1999). The lake's bed profile resembles that of an oil lamp – the deepest point is conical and approximately 14 meters deep, and it shallows gradually outward to 2 m. Substantial sediment deposits have collected over the years and, while it is dredged at intervals, dredging is costly and safe disposal of the bottom mud has posed challenges as urban lake deposits contain significant quantities of heavy metals and organic matter (Dissanayake *et al.* 1987; Silva 2003). Following rapid economic growth, the pollution load into Kandy Lake has increased while space for remediation devices has become increasingly scarce. Unlike many cities, Kandy cannot expand, as it is surrounded by hills.

4.3. Distribution and composition of Phytoplankton variations in Batticaloa Lagoon and Kandy Lake

Phytoplankton are photo synthesizing microscopic biotic organisms that inhabit the upper sunlit layer of almost all oceans and bodies of fresh water on Earth. This means phytoplankton must have light from the sun, so they live in the well-lit surface layers (euphotic zone) of oceans and lakes. They are agents for primary production, the creation of organic compounds from carbon dioxide dissolved in the water, a process that sustains the aquatic food web. Phytoplankton form the base of the aquatic food web and are crucial players in the Earth's carbon cycle. Phytoplankton are very diverse, varying from photosynthesising bacteria to plant-like algae to armor-plated coccolithophores. Important groups of phytoplankton include the diatoms, cyanobacteria, and dinoflagellates, although many other groups are represented.

(<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Phytoplankton>).

4.3.1. Phytoplankton identified at genus lever at the sampling location A (Eravur) in June, and November 2021

June 2021 (dry season)

At the sampling location A (Eravur) during dry season (June, 2021) 27 numbers of phytoplankton members were identified which are;

Microcystis, Hydrodictyon & Microcystis, Pediastrum, Staurastrum, Cosmarium, Spirogyra, Aphanizomenon, Mougiotia, Cyclotella, Navicula, Gyrosigms, Eurorina, Anabaena, Oscillatoria, Euglena, Synedra, Chaetoceros, Scenedesmus, Surirella, Cymbella, Spirulina, Lyngbya, Actinastrum, Volvox, Coscinodiscus, Ankistrodesmus, and Closterium

Microcystis Hydrodictyon Pediastrum Staurastrum Cosmarium Spirogyra & Microcystis

Aphanizomenon Mougiotia Cyclotella Navicula Gyrosigms Eurorina

Anabaena Oscillatoria Euglena Synedra Chaetoceros Scenedesmus

Surirella Cymbella Spirulina Lyngbya Actinastrum Volvox

Coscinodiscus Ankistrodesmus Closterium

In this study during dry season the presence of *Microcystis, Spirogyra, Navicula, Gyrosigms, Anabaena, Oscillatoria, Euglena, Synedra, Surirella, Spirulina, Lyngbya, Ankistrodesmu, and Coscinodiscus* at the sampling location A (Eravur) are the indication that the Batticaloalagoon water is polluted. The depth of the sampling location A (Eravur) is less than 1 m. In addition, the fresh water Desmids also identified. The anthropogenic activities of aquatic ecosystem were noted through water quality assessment and the phytoplankton composition.

According to Edward and Ugwumba, (2013) and Onyema, (2013) the presence of *Ankistrodesmusfractus, Aulacoseiragranulata, Biddulphiaeavis, Coscinodiscus specie, Fragilaria species, Navicula species, Pleurosigmadirectum, Synedra nana,*

Surirellasplendida, *Spirogyraafricana*, *Euglena granulata*, *Microcystisaereginosa*, *Oscillatoria* species and *Anabaena* species in the river during the study indicated that it is under pollution pressure. The proliferation of these species could be due to high nutrient concentrations of the river especially in the dry season.

November 2021 (rainy season)

At the sampling location A (Eravur) during rainy season (November, 2021) 19 numbers of phytoplankton members were identified which are;

Microcystis, *Pediastrum*, *Staurastrum*, *Cosmarium*, *Cyclotella*, *Navicula*, *Gyrosigms*, *Eurorina*, *Anabaena*, *Euglena*, *Synedra*, *Chaetoceros*, *Oscillatoria*, *Scenedesmus*, *Surirella*, *Cymbella*, *Lyngbya*, *Actinastrum* and *Coscinodiscus*

The number of phytoplankton members were reduced at the sampling location A (Eravur) during rainy season, but the pollution indicating species were identified. The Phytoplankton biomass was higher in the dryseason compared to the rainy season and could be the reason of higher water temperature. The depth of the sampling location B (Koddamunai bridge area) is in-between 2 to 3 m. Compare to the sampling location A, the sampling location B is higher.

According to Okogwu and Ugwumba, (2013) decline in phytoplankton biomass in the rainy season could be due to higher flow rate, lower nutrient concentrations and lower water temperature. Flow rate was generally higher in the rainy season due to increased volume of water in the rivers than in the dry season. High flow rate can increase dissolved solid load which limit light penetration for phytoplankton production (Gosselain, Descy, and Everbecq, 1994) in the rainy season.

4.3.2. Phytoplankton identified in genus lever at B (Koddamunai bridge area) in June, and November 2021

June 2021 (dry season)

At the sampling location B (Koddamunai bridge area) during dry season (June, 2021) 36 numbers of phytoplankton members were identified which are;

Tropidoneis, *Asterionellopsis*, *Coscinodiscus*, *Cymbella*, *Stephanodiscus*,
Oscillatoria, *Fragilaria*, *Rhizosolania*, *Melosira*, *Gymnodinium*, *Pediastrum*,
Staurastrum, *Microcystis*, *Ceratium*, *Chaetoceros*, *Ditylum*, *Aphanizomenon*, *Cerataulina*,
Thalassiosira, *Pleurosigma*, *Dinobryon*, *Bacteriastrum*, *Skeletonema*, *Licmophora*, *Entomoneis*,
Corethron, *Spirulina*, *Anabaena*, *Nodularia*, *Navicula*, *Nitzschia*, *Pinnularia*,
Biddulphia, *Synedra*, *Euglena*, and *Phagus*

Tropidoneis Asterionellopsis Coscinodiscus Cymbella Stephanodiscus Oscillatoria

Fragilaria Rhizosolania Melosira Gymnodinium Pediastrum Staurastrum

Microcystis Ceratium Chaetoceros Ditylum Aphanizomenon Cerataulina

Thalassiosira Pleurosigma Dinobryon Bacteriastrum Skeletonema Licmophora

Entomoneis Corithron Spirulina Anabaena Nodularia Navicula

Nitzschia Pinnularia Biddulphia Synedra Euglena Phagus

November 2021 (rainy season)

At the sampling location B (Koddamunai bridge area) during rainy season (November, 2021) 29 numbers of phytoplankton members were identified which are;

Tropidoneis, *Asterionellopsis*, *Coscinodiscus*, *Cymbella*, *Stephanodiscus*, *Oscillatoria*,
Fragilaria, *Rhizosolania*, *Melosira*, *Gymnodinium*, *Pediastrum*, *Staurastrum*, *Microcystis*,
Ceratium, *Chaetoceros*, *Ditylum*, *Aphanizomenon*, *Cerataulina*, *Thalassiosira*, *Pleurosigma*,

Skeletonema, Licmophora, Anabaena, Navicula, Nitzchia, Pinnularia, Biddulphia, Synedra, and Euglena

Tropidoneis Asterionellopsis Coscinodiscus Cymbella Stephanodiscus Oscillatoria

Fragilaria Rhizosolania Melosira Gymnodinium Pediastrum Staurastrum

Microcystis Ceratium Chaetoceros Ditylum Aphanizomenon Cerataulina

Thalassiosira Pleurosigma Skeletonema Licmophora Anabaena Navicula

Nitzchia Pinnularia Biddulphia Synedra Euglena

The following phytoplankton members *Dinobryon, Bacteriastrum, Nodularia, Entomoneis, Corethron, Spirulina* and *Phagus* were not identified or missing. The sampling location B (Koddamunai bridge area) is located 5.4 Km away from bar mouth (Palameenmadu). During dry season more marine forms were identified but during rainy season due to the dilution of salinity or the salinity variation could have caused the disappearance of some phytoplankton members. Both freshwater and marine phytoplankton organisms have been shown to respond strongly to salinity gradients (Kinne. 1971).

4.3.3. Phytoplankton identified in genus lever at A (Kandy City Center area) in June, and November 2021

June 2021 (dry season)

At the sampling location A (Kandy City Center area) during dry season (June, 2021) 08 numbers of phytoplankton members were identified which are;

Aulacoseira, Microcystis, Pediastrum, Merismopedia, Melosira, Diatoma, Anabaena, Euglena

Aulacoseira Microcystis Pediastrum Merismopedia Melosira Diatoma

Anabaena Euglena

Out of these phytoplankton members, *Microcystis* and *Melosira* were found in high density indicating the eutrophic nature of the Kandy Lake.

November 2021 (rainy season)

At the sampling location A (Kandy City Center area) during rainy season (November, 2021) the same 08 numbers of phytoplankton members were identified which are;

Aulacoseira, Microcystis, Pediastrum, Merismopedia, Melosira, Diatoma, Anabaena, Euglena

Aulacoseira Microcystis Pediastrum Merismopedia Melosira Diatoma

Anabaena Euglena

In the rainy season the density of the phytoplankton members were reduced.

4.3.4. Phytoplankton identified in genus lever at B (Department of Immigration and Emigration area) in June, and November 2021

June 2021 (dry season)

At the sampling location B (Department of Immigration and Emigration area) during dry season (June, 2021) the same 08 numbers of phytoplankton members were identified which are;

Aulacoseira, Microcystis, Pediastrum, Merismopedia, Melosira, Diatoma, Anabaena, Euglena

Aulacoseira Microcystis Pediastrum Merismopedia Melosira Diatoma

Anabaena *Euglena*

Out of these phytoplankton members, *Microcystis* and *Melosira* were found in high density indicating the eutrophic nature of the Kandy Lake.

November 2021 (rainy season)

At the sampling location B (Department of Immigration and Emigration area) during rainy season (November, 2021) the same 08 numbers of phytoplankton members were identified which are;

Aulacoseira, *Microcystis*, *Pediastrum*, *Merismopedia*, *Melosira*, *Diatoma*, *Anabaena*, *Euglena*

Aulacoseira *Microcystis* *Pediastrum* *Merismopedia* *Melosira* *Diatoma*

Anabaena *Euglena*

In the rainy season the density of the phytoplankton members was considerably reduced. Most of the dominant species of phytoplankton were not considered as harmful and dangerous for human health. However, certain species of *Anabaena*, *Microcystis*, *Oscillatoria* are known to produce certain toxins.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Batticaloa Lagoon and Kandy Lake are two entirely different water bodies in every aspect.

Batticaloa Lagoon is a very large estuarine lagoon with brackish water in Batticaloa District, Eastern Province, Sri Lanka. The city of Batticalia is located on land between the lagoon and the Indian Ocean. Batticaloa lagoon is a long and narrow lagoon situated in the East coast of Sri

Lanka with the total area is approximately 11,500 ha of water. The Surface area is 141.18 sq. kilometers and the highest depth is 4 meters. The lagoon is 56 km long and opens into the sea at two points. One in the southern end of the lagoon at Periyakallar and the other is midway of the lagoon at Palameenmadu which is close to the Batticaloa town. The depth of the shallow areas is about 0.3 m, whereas in lagoon mouth regions it is recorded as 6.5 m. When compare to previous year (2020) increase in the pollution level was recorded this year (2021) in Batticaloa Lagoon. Last year most of the areas were under lockdown-imposed curfew for a long period. This may be the reason for low pollution level in 2020. In 2021 it was lifted.

The number of phytoplankton at the sampling location A (Eravur) and B (Koddamunai bridge are) of Batticaloa Lagoon in dry season were high compare to rainy season.

Kandy Lake is a freshwater ornamental artificial Lake in the heart of the hill city of Kandy, Sri Lanka. The total surface area is 19ha. The surface area is 0.006544 sq. kilometers. The circumference is 3.21 km. The highest depth is 18.5 meters. The parapet wall giving the appearance of a cloud. Anthropogenic activities on surrounding catchments of the lake may result different physicochemical conditions leading to severe environmental issues. Kandy Lake is artificial and was created in 1807 by Sri Wickrama Rajasinha, the last ruler of the kingdom of Kandy.

The number of phytoplankton at the sampling location A (Kandy City Centre area) and B (Department of Immigration & Emigration area) of Kandy Lake in dry season and rainy season were same but the density of the phytoplankton members was reduced in rainy season.

During the study period in the year 2021, no algal bloom was recorded at both sampling stations of Batticaloa Lagoon and Kandy Lake.

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